

Morphological Analysis of Osmanabad Town: A Geographical Study

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Abstract

The main objectives of the study are to find out the morphological analysis of Osmanabad town. It also includes table & figure analysis of town in Osmanabad district. For preparing a plan for any city for its future growth, it is necessary to know the existing land use pattern, social facilities and infrastructural facilities. The kind of survey is able to bring on the foreground of the existing condition and also to decide future line of action. Data will be collected from primary and secondary sources.

Keywords: Morphology, Land use Planning

Introduction

For preparing a plan for any city for its future growth, it is necessary to know the existing land use pattern, functional arrangement and condition of existing civic amenities, social facilities, and infrastructural facilities and also inter relationship between the above components in the physical planning. The kind of survey is able to bring on the foreground of the existing condition and also to decide future line of action.

Objectives

- 1) The main objective of the study is to Table and figure analysis of town in Osmanabad District
- 2) Find out the morphological analysis of Osmanabad Town.

Methodology

- 1) Data will be collected from primary and secondary sources.
- 2) Use the Socio-Economic Abstract & District census handbook of Osmanabad district 1961-2001.
- 3) Chose the random sample of eight town level places.
- 4) Spatial characteristic of morphology of town on the basic of data available

Study Area

The district of Osmanabad southern most districts in Aurangabad division of Maharashtra State situated between 17° 37' to 18° 42' North Latitudes and 75° 17' to 76° 47' East Longitudes. The district has an area of 7484 Sq KM. About 7271 Sq KM. area (96.79%) is known as rural area where as only 241.4 Sq KM (3.21%) area comes under urban categories.

Osmanabad is district headquarter and Class II town of the study area. The latitudinal extension of the town is 17° 35' to 18° 40' north and longitudinal extension is 75° 16' to 76° 40' east. The municipal area of the town is 1206.00 hectares and population according to 2001 census is 80,625 persons.

Existing and Proposed Land use

The total area within the Osmanabad Municipal limit is 1206.00 hectares. Out of which

55.65 percent is developed area in existing landuse and in proposed landuse it is 88.13 percent. (Table No. 1.1 & Fig. No. 1.1, 1.2) The breakup of existing land use shows that 33.18 percent area is under residential use, 1.49 percent area is under industrial use, 9.90 percent area is under public and semi public amenities use, 1.72 percent area is under commercial use, 1.39 percent area is under open spaces, 7.07 percent area is under transport and communication use and is 0.87 percent area is under public utility use of the total municipal area.

Functional Zones of Osmanabad Town

1) Residential Area: The residential area is existing in all sectors. In the existing landuse, area under residential use in the town is 400.17 hectares i.e. 33.18 percent of the total municipal area. By considering the future growth of the town, in proposed landuse 666.00 hectares area is allocated to residential use which is 55.22 percent to total municipal area.

As per 2001 census, there were near about 14587 houses existing in Osmanabad city. These are categorized according to the future life of the structures into four categories i.e. A.B.C.D.

A. Future life of structure above 60 year = 5% of the total structures.

B. Future life of structure between 40-60 year = 30% of the total structures

C. Future life of structure between 15-40 year -30% of the total structures

D. Future life of structure below 15 years 35% of the total structures.

The most of the structures in gaathan & congested area of the city are old.

The slums are in the form of hutments, where there is no proper light, ventilation and other sanitary condition etc. It is generally observed that the land owner converts the plots irregular shape and of substandard area and sale them out to the needy person without having proper planning for their land.

Table No.1.1 Osmanabad Town: Existing and Proposed Landuse

Sr.No.	Landuse	Existing Landuse		Proposed Landuse	
		Area in Hectares	Percentage to total Municipal area	Area in Hectares	Percentage to total Municipal area
1	Residential	400.17	33.18	666	55.22
2	Commercial	20.84	1.73	22.34	1.85
3	Industries	18	1.49	1.28	0.11
4	Transport & Communication	85.33	7.08	91.96	7.62
5	Public Utility	10.55	0.87	13.38	1.11
6	Public & Semi Public amenities	119.49	9.91	181.18	15
7	Open spaces	16.81	1.39	86.77	7.22
	Total Developed Area	671.19	55.65	1062.91	88.13
8	Area under Water spread	14.96	1.24	15.89	1.32
9	Area under agricultural & open use.	470.64	39.02	127.2	10.5
10	Vacant and barren land	49.21	4.08
	Total undeveloped area	534.81	44.52	143.09	11.82
	Total Municipal Area	1206	100	1206	100

Source: District Town Planning office, Osmanabad District.

This has resulted in unplanned development having no public amenities, no proper roads and sanitation for healthy development of the town. To checkup and improvements of such development a timely control is very necessary. Municipal council, Fig. No. 1.1 Osmanabad Town: Existing Landuse

Osmanabad has provided a list and map of notified slums. There are 18 notified slums declared in Osmanabad district, which includes an area in km. about 13.8 kilometers and shows 11474 of the population of Osmanabad city is living.

Fig. No.1.2 Osmanabad Town: Proposed Landuse

II)

Commercial Area: In the existing landuse, area under commercial use is 20.84 hectares i.e. 1.73 percent of the total municipal area. By considering the future growth of the town, in proposed landuse 22.34 hectares area is allocated to commercial use which is 1.85 percent to total municipal area.

Kala Maruti is the core area of commercial activity. (Fig. No. 6.5) Market yard is also a big commercial center for agriculture produce commodities. Other than this, shopping centers are developed on the rim of Bus stop, near Govt. Hospital, Shivaji chowk, & along Latur, Tuljapur, Beed and Barshi roads.

Osmanabad city has the famous 'Bus Stop' as the central place of the city. The main centre of the Bus Stop is a huge two-storied structure. In the middle of the circular structure is the temple of Goddess Maruti. There are 04 roads connecting to this Bus Stop and along these roads are separate markets selling all kinds of traditional local wares such as gold ornaments to footwear and food items from chilli to jaggery. Thus, the 'Bus Stop' has become C.B.D. (Central Business District) area of the town.

III) Industrial Area: In the existing landuse, area under industrial use is 18.00 hectares i.e. 1.49 percent of the total municipal area. By considering the future growth of the town, in proposed landuse 1.28 hectares area is allocated to industrial use which is 0.11 percent to total municipal area. A total industrial area about 18.00 hectares is provided in the revised draft development plan of Osmanabad.

At present industrial area is MIDC area. There are dal mills, oil mills, hosiery units, building material units, etc. in MIDC area. There are some saw mills existing in the eastern part of the town on Latur road.

IV) Transport and Communication Area: In the existing landuse, area under transport & communication use is 85.33 hectares i.e. 7.07 percent of the total municipal area. By considering the future growth of the town, in proposed landuse 91.96 hectares area is allocated to Transport & Communication use which is 7.62 percent to total municipal area.

The city is connected with trade routes to important commercial centres such as Solapur, Kolhapur, Pune, Beed, Ahmadnagar, Aurangabad and Kurudwadi by way of National highways namely the Dhule-Solapur (NH-211) and Mumbai-Hydrabad highways respectively.

The commercial activities of the city are mostly concentrated at the Kala Maruti, the Shivaji Chowk, and the Ambedkar chowk. The Bus stop is the major shopping and trading centre and is located in the heart of the city and also is considered the central part of the city. Heavy congestion of vehicular traffic is generally observed near the ST stand, old Railway station, Samta chowk, Gandhi Nagar, Central Bulding and Barshi naka.

The new broad gauge railway line from Kurudwadi-Osmanabad junction is being converted to Mumbai-Pune-Osmanabad a broad gauge line, this line further connects Osmanabad road station.

V) Public Utility Area: In the existing landuse, area under public utility use is 10.55 hectares i.e. 0.87 percent of the total municipal area. By considering the future growth of the town, in proposed landuse 13.38 hectares area is allocated to public utility use which is 1.11 percent to total municipal area.

Existing burial grounds are situated in old gaathan area. Cremation ground is situated near the Khaja Shamshoddin gazi temple and Chambar leni and Raje Bag near Ambedkar Chowk. The existing cremation grounds are small in area therefore

extension to these have been proposed in the revised development plan.

There are only one municipal gardens, the Raje Bag. Newly developed Hatla Devi temple is near about 5 km. of Osmanabad District.

VI) Public and Semipublic Area: In the existing landuse, area under public & semi public use is 119.49 hectares i.e. 9.90 percent of the total municipal area. By considering the future growth of the town, in proposed landuse 181.18 hectares area is allocated to public & semi public use which is 15.00 percent to total municipal area.

Osmanabad is a leading educational center in Marathwada region. Osmanabad city has development "Osmanabad pattern" in educational fields, 24 primary schools & 05 high schools, three Arts, commerce and science degree colleges, engineering college, medical college, Boys & Girls Govt. polytechnic, Boys & Girls I.T.I., B.Ed. college, Law college are existing in the city and Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar University sub centre of Osmanabad District.

It is observed that most of the primary schools and High schools are located in rental premises, having no sufficient playground. Hence the existing primary schools and High schools are not sufficient to meet the demands of the educational facilities as per the norms. There are 3 cinema theaters, one town hall of municipal council, recreational halls like Shubh Mangal Karyalay, Akshata Mangal Karyalaya, Pushpak Mangal Karyalaya, Yeshraj Mangal Karyalaya and Hatlai Mangal Karyalaya etc. are existing within the city. At present water is supplied to the city with tap from sai water jack well and through Terna project and also supplied through 712 tube wells. The scheme is designated for population of 1.00 lakhs and the water is supplied at the rate of 80 lit/capita/day The required rate of water supply as per norms is 135 lit/capita /day.

The power supply to the city is made from Girvali 220 sub-station (Parli dermal grid). The help of 5535 mercury lights, 6596 sodium vapour lamps, Industrial ligh 4879, Agriculture lights 49254 and 3385 tube lights illuminates the city. There are 28327 electric consumers of all types consuming electric load of 74.99 Million kilowatt Ms.

Conclusions

In the existing landuse, area under commercial use is 20,84 hectares is. 1.73. percent of the total municipal area. By considering the future growth of the town, in proposed landuse 22,34 hectares area is allocated to commercial use which is 125 percent to total municipal area. In the existing landuse, area under industrial use is 18.00 hectares i.e. 1.49 percent of the total municipal area. By considering the future growth of the town, in proposed landuse 1.28 hectares area is allocated to industrial use which is 0.11 percent to total municipal area. In the existing landuse, area under transport & communication use is 85.33 hectares i.e. 7.07 percent of the total municipal area. By considering the future growth of the town, in proposed landuse 91.96 hectares area is allocated to Transport & Communication use which is 7.62 percent to total municipal are In the existing landuse, area under public utility use is 10.55 hectares ie. 0.27 percent of the total municipal area. By considering the future growth of the town, in proposed landuse 13.38 hectares area is allocated to public utility use which is 1.11 percent to total municipal area. In the existing landuse, area under public & semi public use is 119.49 hectares i.c. 9.90 percent of the total municipal area. By considering the future growth of the town, in proposed landuse 181.18 hectares area is allocated to public & semi public use which is 15.00 percent to total municipal area.

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